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Coordinator	University of Pavia (UNIPV)
Deliverable Lead Partner	PUT
Contributing Partners	DEON, UoH, UNIPV, NKI
Contact	Prof. Silvana Quaglino
Email	silvana.quaglino@unipv.it
Website	www.capable-project.eu

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1. Versions History

Version	Date	Author	Comments
0.1	23/05/2022	SW	Initial draft
0.2	1/06/2022	SW	Revisions of the structure
0.5	11/06/2022	SW	Preparation of detailed clinical scenarios
0.8	30/06/2022	SW	Detailed description of Virtual Coach and PROforma CIGs
0.9	6/07/2022	SW	Revision and extension of the content
1.0	10/07/2022	SW	Version ready for the review
2.0	23/07/2022	SW	Final version revised after the review
2.1	24/07/2022	SQ	Minor changes and corrections before submission

2. Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to demonstrate the current state of the Virtual Coach (VC) -- a patient coaching component of the CAPABLE system. VC provides active and comprehensive support for patients and their home caregivers. The provided support referred to as *coaching*, involves monitoring reported symptoms and readings obtained from wearable sensors (consumer-grade smartwatches), recommending pharmacological (only if already prescribed by the doctors) and non-pharmacological interventions (so-called *well-being capsules*), and delivering alerts, reminders and various types of tips (related to prevention, education, and symptom management).

This demonstration comprises a textual description and a video. The text in this document presents the current architecture of VC based on the actor model paradigm, describes the adopted approach to modeling and dynamic, event-driven execution of computer-interpretable guidelines (CIGs), and summarizes two clinical scenarios that are employed to illustrate the operations of VC and related CAPABLE components, such as KDOM or Deontics Engine (DE). These operations are then presented in the video available at the following link: https://capable-project.eu/d5-5_demo/.

The structure of this document is as follows. In Section 3 we define the scope of demonstration -- in particular, we explain what VC interventions are covered by the presented scenarios. In Section 4 we provide an overview of the current state of VC from the architectural perspective. In Section 5 we present the two considered scenarios and conclude with the summary in Section 6.

3. Scope of the Demonstration

The clinical scenarios covered by this demonstration assume patients who experience two frequent adverse reactions to cancer treatment -- diarrhea and pruritus. The scenarios have been crafted to illustrate a variety of interventions delivered by VC, such as:

- Capsule recommendations customized for the clinical goals selected as part of the shared clinical decision-making (e.g., during the patient enrollment) and for hobbies reported by the patient.
- Pharmacological treatment recommendations based on the currently applied CIGs.
- Prevention and management tips associated with the current treatment and ongoing symptoms.
- Reminders about upcoming visits and notifications about new and updated medication prescriptions.
- Symptom reporting and form-fill-in requests.
- Additional non-pharmacological recommendations, such as experience sharing or a “need help” thermometer.
- Motivational messages associated with selected capsules.
- Educational materials (so-called infographics) suited for patient characteristics and conditions (e.g., prescribed treatment, reported symptoms).

Here we would like to explain that VC is a backend component -- it does not have its own user interface (UI), but generates FHIR resources (e.g., `Communication`, `MedicationRequest` or `ServiceRequest`) that are stored in the Data Platform (DP) and later processed by the mobile Patient App (PtApp). The UI developed for the CAPABLE system is described in another deliverable (see D6.3 for details) and it is outside the scope of this demonstration. Therefore, the video is limited to the logs of VC and the CAPABLE simulator that executes prepared clinical scenarios and verifies their outcomes.

4. Overview of the Virtual Coach

VC has been already described in previously published deliverables, and specifically in D2.2 (Peleg et al., 2021) we defined a set of requirements and preliminary architecture for this component, while in D5.2 (Gilboa-Solomon et al., 2021) we presented the scheme of major VC operations. Thus, to avoid repetitions, the following description provides a general overview necessary to understand the demonstration and gives details for changes introduced after the publication of D5.2.

Similar to the Physician DSS (PDSS) presented in D5.3, VC employs the PROforma formalism (Sutton and Fox, 2003) to represent the clinical knowledge that drives the coaching process. PROforma is based on a task-network model, where possible basic tasks include enquiries, decisions, and actions. It also allows for grouping tasks into more complex plans (for additional details see D5.2). This knowledge captured by PROforma covers clinical guidelines, workflows (or processes), and rules. For simplicity, we will refer to all of them as CIGs, although some workflows are not directly concerned with evidence-based management of specific conditions, and they play an auxiliary role, e.g., they are responsible for generating symptom reporting requests or visit reminders.

CIGs represented in PROforma are executed by the Deontics Engine (DE). More specifically, we employ a hybrid approach where DE is responsible for traversing a CIG, identifying active tasks waiting for execution (based on scheduling constraints and preconditions), confirming these tasks (marking them as completed), and executing selected autonomous tasks (e.g., setting default values of data items), while VC is responsible for executing the active tasks. This results in a flexible CIG execution platform that can communicate with other CAPABLE components and can be extended to handle non-standard CIG tasks (e.g., requiring complex internal computations).

4.1. Actor Model-based Architecture

VC is designed and implemented following the *actor model* (Charousset et al., 2013) where the functionality of a system is divided into multiple independent entities called *actors*. Actors work in parallel, communicate asynchronously by exchanging messages and form a multi-level hierarchy where actors at higher levels supervise those at lower levels (if an actor at a lower level terminates unexpectedly, the supervisor may restore it). Conceptually, actors are similar to agents constituting a multi-agent system, however, they are lighter in terms of the computational load and more concerned with performance and robustness than with intelligent autonomous operations and sophisticated interaction protocols (Cardoso et al., 2013).

In Figure 1 we present the high-level architecture of VC and identify the other relevant components of the CAPABLE system it interacts with, either directly, through a dedicated REST API, or indirectly, through the Data Platform (DP) and the Case Manager (CM). For clarity and brevity, only the main classes of actors are included (some of them are further specialized, see D2.2 and D5.2 for details, and several auxiliary classes are omitted). Below we provide a short description of specific classes:

- *Case Manager Adapter* -- interacts with CM and notifies other actors (using an internal subscription mechanism) about reported events.
- *Deontics Engine Adapter* -- interacts with DE to facilitate the execution of CIGs.

- *Data Platform Adapter* -- interacts with DP to retrieve and store FHIR resources capturing clinical data and messages to other CAPABLE components.
- *Coaching Controller* -- manages the coaching process for all patients handled by VC, responds to CM events, and initiates the generation of intervention recommendations, it also schedules execution of CIGs by ensuring their parallel or serial execution depending on pre-specified requirements.
- *CIG Executor* -- manages the execution of specific CIGs and communicates with DE via the Deontics Engine Adapter.
- *Task Executor* -- manages the execution of a specific CIG task, communicates with DE via the Deontics Engine Adapter, and may interact with DP via the Data Platform Adapter and invoke new CIGs via the Coaching Controller.

Figure 1. High-level architecture of VC. In brackets, we provide the number of actors from each class that exists in VC -- 1 means exactly one instance (singleton), and 0+ indicates 0 or more instances

Moreover, in Figure 1 we indicate the number of actors from each class that exists in VC during its operations. Some actors -- annotated with (1) -- are singletons. Their single instances are created when VC starts and then persist until VC stops. Examples include all adapter actors that interact with other CAPABLE components. On the other hand, actors marked with (0+) are created on the fly depending on the current workload and terminate when they are no longer necessary (thus it is possible that no instance of such class exists at a given time). Specifically, a new instance of CIG Executor is created for each invoked CIG, thus VC is able to handle simultaneously multiple CIGs for multiple patients. Moreover, a new instance of Task Executor is created for each starting task from executed CIGs, so VC can execute in parallel multiple tasks from a given CIG if this is allowed according to sequencing constraints. Finally,

a new instance of Data Value Collector is created for each data item that should be obtained from external sources, e.g., KDOM or DP, so that values can be collected simultaneously.

As described above, VC operates in a highly parallel manner. While this is desired in most cases, there are certain situations where duplicated recommendations may be generated. Specifically, this may happen if a CIG responsible for generating a specific recommendation is triggered by multiple events, such as passing time and new patient data. For example, prevention tips associated with various types of therapies (e.g., immunotherapy or targeted therapy) should be sent to patients on regular basis (every 3 days) or when a new relevant treatment is prescribed. If both events were reported at the same time, then two instances of the same CIG would be executed in parallel, and two tips would be generated. A simple solution of checking DP for an existing Communication resource with the already generated tip would not work, as both checks might be performed before writing the resource to DP. To avoid this issue, it is possible to mark a CIG as requiring serial execution. Then, the Coaching Controller actor will ensure that only a single instance of this CIG is executed for a given patient at a given time.

4.2. Dynamic Execution of PROforma CIGs

In VC we adopt a dynamic instantiation and execution of CIGs. CIG instances (enactments in PROforma terms) are created in response to specific events and terminated as soon as these events have been handled. In this way, VC does not need to store any internal state information, such as the list of CIGs being applied to currently managed patients and relies solely on data stored in DP. Such a solution simplifies the operations of VC and increases its robustness, as restarts do not require recovering or rebuilding this internal state. Moreover, VC does not need to be restarted in order to use an updated CIG.

We also use two levels of CIGs -- *primary* with a single *master* CIG, and *secondary* -- with multiple *specialized* CIGs. The master CIG is presented in Figure 2. This CIG is invoked in response to events raised by CM and defined by CM rules. First, it checks if there exists a plan to handle the reported event (see Figure 2a). Then, it retrieves the context of an event (i.e., the properties of FHIR resources associated with the event, see Figure 2b) and then invokes these specific CIGs whose activation conditions are matched by the context (see Figure 2c).

(a) plans to handle specific event reported by CM (one plan per event, the event name is checked in the plan preconditions)- rt=radiotherapy

(b) plan *new_observation* to handle the event associated with a new Observation resource (in *check_new_observation* the characteristics of the event is retrieved)

(c) plan *manage_symptom* to handle reported symptoms. Individual action tasks invoke specialized CIGs, and more than one CIG may be invoked by a given event

Figure 2. The master CIG used by VC

For example, the *new-observation* event that corresponds to storing a new Observation resource in DP is reported by CM. This invokes the master CIG and the right plan is identified. Then, the context is checked -- it includes such properties of the resource as code, value, and source. If the code corresponds to pruritus or rash, and the value is not "absent", then the specific CIG for pruritus/rash is invoked and executed. Moreover, if the source is PtApp (i.e., the symptom was entered by the patient or the home caregiver), then the specialized *contact level* CIG is invoked.

If the reported event is associated with a specific patient, then the patient ID is passed to the specialized CIG, so it operates on this patient. In addition to the patient ID, the master CIG may also pass references to resources associated with the reported event, so that the specialized CIG may easily retrieve them from DP and further process them if needed.

In Figure 3 we present the specialized CIG for pruritus/rash. It starts with checking the resource associated with the event in order to identify the specific symptom that was reported (multiple symptoms may trigger this CIG) and retrieves the current values of other related symptoms. Then, it provides management tips (possibly more than one) appropriate for the current clinical status of the patient.

(a) the main plan to handle pruritus, rash, and other associated symptoms reported by the patient and clinician

(b) *provide_tip_if_reported_by_patient* plan to provide tips for a symptom reported by the patient. Individual tasks generate appropriate management tips (ge=greater or equal)

Figure 3. The specialized CIG for pruritus/rash

Splitting the clinical knowledge into the master and multiple specialized CIGs results in simpler CIGs that are easier to create and maintain (update), as they focus on specific and well-defined issues. This, combined with the dynamic CIG execution facilitates runtime updates of the domain knowledge used by VC, as smaller “portions” of this knowledge need to be revised. Moreover, it is easy to add new specialized CIGs to the system or revise activation conditions for already considered specialized CIGs, as such changes are limited to uploading new CIGs to the repository and referencing them in the master CIG.

As already mentioned, DE and VC together offer a flexible environment for executing CIGs. In order to control it and to provide the required scope of coaching, we have extended the description of CIG tasks and data items by introducing new meta-properties. They are specified at the level of PROforma representation and then processed by VC.

Below we present some of the meta-properties that are relevant for the demonstration presented in this document and focus on these associated with tasks. Each action task in a CIG is further characterized by the *intervention type* that indicates the type of intervention recommended by this task. Currently supported types are presented in Table 1. Most of these interventions result in creating a Communication resource sent to PtApp that further presents its content to the user. The only exception is *cig-invocation* which results in invoking the indicated specialized CIG. Such interventions are used mostly in the master CIG.

Type	Description	Requires response
medication-proposal	A proposal to start a medication or a set of medications	✓
capsule-proposal	A proposal to start a well-being capsule	✓
medication-update	A notification about a new or updated medication prescription	
caregiver-contact	A recommendation to contact a health caregiver with additional instructions (so-called <i>contact level</i>)	
prevention-tip	An educational tip related to symptom prevention, provided before the patient experiences a symptom	
management-tip	An educational tip related to symptom management, provided after the patient has reported a symptom	
infographic-tip	An educational tip pointing to infographic related to a specific treatment and symptom. Augments information provided in prevention and management tips	
help-thermometer	A recommendation to use the “need help” thermometer for minor, but physically annoying, persistent symptoms and to contact a health caregiver	✓
symptom-report	A request to provide an update on a symptom that has been already reported as ongoing	✓
form-fill-in	A request to fill in a given form used to obtain additional information needed for proper patient management and evaluation	✓
experience-sharing	A recommendation to share experience on the patient forum after a symptom has resolved	
visit-reminder	A reminder about an upcoming (next 24 hours) appointment with the health caregiver	
cig-invocation	Invocation of a secondary CG	

Table 1. Types of interventions currently supported by VC (the requires response column indicates whether the intervention requires a more complex response from the patient than acknowledging the message)

The categorization is very detailed to facilitate checking for specific interventions (captured by Communication resources) in DP. When presenting interventions to the patient, PtApp clusters them in larger groups. We would also like to emphasize that *medication-proposal* intervention is limited to the treatments that have been already approved by the clinician (as-

needed medications that may be started due to the patient’s condition) and VC is not allowed to recommend new treatments on its own.

Moreover, each enquiry task is characterized by *enquiry type* that specifies whether data items associated with the task should be provided (computed internally) by VC or retrieved from an external source, e.g., DP. Supported enquiry types are presented in Table 2. Internal enquiries allow enhancing CIGs with additional functions implemented inside VC. We use internal enquiries as “extension points” because data items computed by VC are passed back to CIGs and used by other CIG tasks (e.g., by action tasks that generate interventions). Internal enquiries are realized by specialized actors derived from Task Executor that act as wrappers around complex computations or knowledge repositories. For example, capsule selection is handled by the *Capsule Enquiry Task Executor* actor that employs an algorithm solving the set covering problem (it searches for the smallest set of capsules that address all clinical goals for the patient and match the patient’s hobbies).

We should note that some of the internal enquiries – internal-contact-level and internal-prevention-tip (see Table 2) -- may be modeled directly in PROforma as multiple action tasks with preconditions, however, such resulting CIGs would be very complex (with more than 40 tasks corresponding to recommendations) and difficult to maintain. Introducing repositories with possible tips and their applicability conditions that are then processed by VC in order to “compute” (select) appropriate tips simplify the CIGs responsible for these two types of interventions (prevention-tip and caregiver-contact – see Table 1). Moreover, these repositories are created automatically from spreadsheets provided by clinical experts what facilitates their maintenance.

Type	Description
external	Values should be retrieved from sources “external” to VC -- DP or KDOM (detailed source is specified by meta-data associated with data items)
internal	Values should be generated internally by VC by running a personalized prediction model, performing some computations, or checking internal knowledge resources or repositories. This type is specialized to one of the following types given below
internal-capsules	Select capsules appropriate for selected clinical goals and hobbies indicated by the patient
internal-contact-level	Select a contact level appropriate for a reported symptom and its value (so-called description)
internal-prevention-tip	Selected a random prevention tip relevant for the current therapy from a collection of tips based on the educational materials from AIMAC

Table 2. Types of enquiries currently supported by VC

Finally, we would like to note that the set of interaction and enquiry types is not closed and it can be further extended to cover new capabilities introduced by VC.

4.3. Interactions Between Actors

In Figure 4 we demonstrate interactions between actors in VC -- they are summarized below (in the text we refer to specific messages in the flow diagram):

- A new event is reported to Coaching Controller [message 01], and in response, it creates a new instance of CIG Executor to execute the master CIG [02].
- CIG Executor executes a CIG (both master and specialized one) in a loop. It first gets a list of active tasks [03], and then for each task, it creates a new instance of Task Executor [04] -- its operations depend on the type of task and are detailed in subsequent bullets. Completed tasks are marked as such in DE (20) and CIG Executor terminates when all tasks in the CIG have been completed.
- Execution of an action task further depends on its intervention type (see Table 1). If it is *cig-invocation*, then Task Executor sends a request to Coaching Controller to start a specialized CIG [05]. In the case of *medication-proposal* or *capsule-proposal*, a corresponding draft Request resource (MedicationRequest or ServiceRequest, respectively) is stored in DP [06]. Then, Task Executor requests GoCom to mitigate possible interactions between the proposal and ongoing treatments [07, 08] -- currently, this is done only for medications, however, there is ongoing work to extend GoCom to capsules. Finally, Task Executor creates a Communication with the proposal that points either to the initial ServiceRequest (capsules) or MedicationRequest checked and possibly revised by GoCom (medications) [09]. Finally, for other interventions, a corresponding Communication is stored in DP [10].
- Execution of an enquiry task starts with getting data items associated with this task [11]. Further processing depends on the enquiry type (see Table 2). For *external* enquiry, a new instance of Data Value Collector is created for each data item [12] and it retrieves the value directly from DP [13] or requests it from KDOM [14-16]. Collected values are reported to Task Executor [17]. In the case of *internal* enquiry, Task Executor obtains values by performing some calculations or by checking internal data/knowledge repositories [18]. Finally, all collected values are stored in DE [19].

We would like to point out that the decision tasks are currently not handled by VC. While we initially considered them (see D2.2 for the initial proposal), they turned out to be redundant when modeling patient-oriented CIGs. In these CIGs decisions made by the patient are limited to binary choices, and the task precondition mechanism in PROforma provides sufficient expressiveness to specify conditions for these decisions.

Figure 4. Flow diagram with interactions between actors in VC

As indicated in the text above, instances of some actor classes -- CIG Executor, Task Executor, and Data Value Collector are created at runtime as needed. They constitute a hierarchy, where

the creating agent is a parent and created agents are children -- this hierarchy is illustrated in Figure 5. Parent actors supervise their children -- they can restart supervised actors in case of any problems or delete them if they are no longer necessary.

Figure 5. Hierarchy of actors in VC. Root indicates the actor that manages all other user actors. Actors that are direct children of Root are singletons, and we distinguish between instances of other actor classes by providing their instance identifiers (starting with #)

5. Demonstration Scenarios

The scenarios considered in the demonstration were inspired by the scenarios described in D4.1 (Gabetta and Parimbelli, 2020) and D4.2 (Gabetta et al., 2021) that presented a cancer patient treated with immunotherapy and suffering from diarrhea and pruritus/rash, respectively. However, they were revised by removing parts not relevant for VC and by including a wider range of provided VC interventions than in the original deliverables.

In the current scenarios, we present the following interventions recommended by VC:

- Capsule recommendations
- Pharmacological treatment recommendations
- Prevention and management tips and educational materials (infographics)
- Reminders about upcoming visits and notifications about new medication prescriptions
- Symptom reporting and form-fill-in requests
- Additional non-pharmacological recommendations -- experience sharing and a “need help” thermometer
- Motivational messages associated with capsules

In order to execute the demonstration scenarios, we use the CAPABLE simulator (Lanzola et al., 2022) that can simulate the passing time and automatically check actual results produced by CAPABLE components against expected ones. The Simulator traverses through a scenario, uploads provided FHIR resources to DP, and at specified checkpoints, it activates CM and other system components (actually, these components are activated by events reported by CM). Then, it compares FHIR resources written to DP by these components in response to reported events with the resources expected for a given checkpoint, thus asserting or rejecting the checkpoint.

In the video associated with the deliverable, we show the log of VC and the Simulator and demonstrate that all checkpoints in both scenarios have been successfully asserted which means VC has generated all the expected interventions. We would also like to note that these scenarios have been run on the development version of the CAPABLE system (aimed at continuous integration testing) with all other backend components (in particular, KDOM and GoCom) being active.

5.1. Scenario 1 -- Episode of Diarrhea and Abdominal Pain

Here we consider Maria, a female patient (age 68) treated with targeted therapy (sunitinib) and immunotherapy (nivolumab) who suffers an episode of diarrhea and abdominal pain. The scenario is summarized in Figure 6 -- in this figure, we focus on interactions between the patient and VC and we indicate interventions generated by the latter using the types introduced in Table 1. We also show interactions between VC and the physician that result in generated interventions. Please note that for the sake of brevity the interactions are presented at a high level, and we omit some CAPABLE components, such as DP, CM, PDSS, or PtApp that participate in these interactions (see D2.2 for additional details).

As explained in Section 4.2 all VC interventions are generated as the result of invoking the master CIG first, and then some specialized CIGs. However, for simplicity in the text hereafter, we will mention only the specialized CIGs to better show their purpose.

Figure 6. Interactions between VC, patient, and physician in scenario 1 (episode of diarrhea and abdominal pain, blue arrows correspond to VC interventions)

The scenario starts on day 0 when Maria is enrolled for management in the CAPABLE system. At this point available clinical information, including ongoing treatment, is collected, and VC invokes the prevention tip CIG to provide an AIMAC tip specific to current cancer therapy (message [0.1] in Figure 6; we will refer to other messages in this diagram in the subsequent text). Immunotherapy may result in diarrhea, therefore the physician -- following the

recommendation from PDSS -- prescribed loperamide as-needed [0.2]. In response, VC runs the medication update CIG to produce a notification about a new prescription [0.3]. Maria also complains about sleep problems and together with the physician they decide to pursue the clinical goal of sleep improvement [0.4]. VC runs the capsule selection CIG -- the Imagery Training capsule is found as a viable candidate; however, the value of the insomnia sleep index (ISI) is needed to fully recommend it. Therefore, VC sends a form fill-in request to collect it [0.5], and Maria completes the form using PtApp [0.6]. Based on the total score of 17, VC accepts the candidate and sends the capsule proposal to Maria [0.7], who decides to try it out (please note that we will not describe any other capsule-related activities in this scenario -- they will be discussed in the next section).

On day 9 VC sends an AIMAC prevention tip [9.1] -- this is triggered by passing time. After some time, Maria reports grade 1 diarrhea [9.2]. In response, VC invokes the diarrhea CIG and sends a management tip with diarrhea-related self-care instructions [9.3] and a proposal to start loperamide [9.4], ensuring first that it has been earlier prescribed as as-needed medication. Reported diarrhea also triggers the contact level CIG and VC sends a corresponding caregiver contact recommendation to Maria [9.5].

On day 11 VC invokes the symptom update CIG (this is done periodically and triggered by passing time, similarly to the prevention tip CIG) and sends a symptom update request to Maria, since 2 days have passed since diarrhea was reported for the last time [11.1]. Maria responds that the diarrhea is gone/absent [11.2]. VC invokes the experience sharing CIG and sends a corresponding recommendation to the patient [11.3]. Later that day Maria reports grade 1 abdominal pain [11.4] and VC responds with an appropriate caregiver contact recommendation [11.5].

On day 13 VC sends another AIMAC tip [13.1], as 3 days have passed since it was provided for the last time, and Maria provides no feedback.

On day 14 VC sends a request to update information about abdominal pain [14.1] and Maria reports grade 2 [14.2]. In response, VC invokes the relevant CIGs (contact level and help thermometer) and sends recommendations from these CIGs to contact a caregiver [14.3] and consider using the "need help" thermometer tool [14.4]. Since the abdominal pain worries Maria, she decides to contact her physician and the visit is scheduled for day 16 (this is done outside the CAPABLE system).

Finally, on day 15 VC sends Maria a reminder about the upcoming visit [15.1].

5.2. Scenario 2 -- Episode of Pruritus

In this scenario, we consider another patient -- Giulio (male, age 64) -- who experiences an episode of pruritus. The scenario is summarized in Figure 7 and as previously, the diagram focuses on high-level interactions between VC, the patient, and the physician.

The scenario starts at day 0 with Giulio's enrollment, when available clinical information is collected. Following the recommendation from PDSS, the physician decides to start nivolumab (message [0.1] in Figure 7 and other messages are referenced in the text hereafter). In response, VC invokes appropriate CIGs (medication update, infographic, and prevention tip) and generates the following interventions: notification about a new prescription for nivolumab [0.2], a tip pointing to an infographic that discusses the risk of pruritus and rash associated with nivolumab [0.3, the infographic itself is presented in PtApp], and an AIMAC prevention tip [0.4]. Later that day Giulio completes his profile in PtApp and reports his hobby -- walking [0.5].

The cancer treatment proceeds for 4 weeks without any complications or side effects, and during this time VC interventions are limited to periodic sending of prevention tips. Such a tip is also provided in day 30 [30.1]. On that day Giulio has a follow-up visit and meets his physician. Given the low quality of Giulio's sleep and low physical activity reported by the smartwatch that he had received during the enrollment, the physician recommends setting the clinical goals of sleep and physical activity improvement [30.2]. In response, VC runs the capsule selection CIG and proposes the My Daily Walk capsule [30.3], and the patient accepts this recommendation.

On day 31 Giulio reports his first walk [31.1] but he fails to do it in the next few days. Moreover, low numbers of daily steps as reported by the smartwatch indicate Giulio does not practice the capsule activity. Therefore, on day 35 VC invokes the daily walk CIG and sends a management tip to remind Giulio about the capsule and motivate him by presenting the benefits of walking [35.1]. It also sends another AIMAC tip.

On day 36, sensor readings indicate a large number of daily steps -- VC invokes the daily walk CIG and generates a suggestion to report the activity [36.1]. Indeed, Giulio reports it [36.2].

On day 37 Giulio reports grade 1 pruritus, fortunately not accompanied by a rash [37.1]. VC invokes the corresponding CIG and provides a management tip for pruritus when observed by the patient [37.2] -- a different tip is generated if the physician reports this symptom, e.g., during a follow-up visit. Moreover, VC sends another management tip to avoid sun exposure when walking, or even to postpone this activity [37.3].

On day 39 VC sends yet another AIMAC prevention tip [39.1]. It also sends a request to provide an update on pruritus [39.2]. Giulio reports the symptom is gone [39.3]. In response, VC sends a recommendation to share the experience associated with handling this symptom [39.4].

Figure 7. Interactions between VC, patient, and physician in scenario 2 (episode of pruritus, blue arrows correspond to VC interventions)

6. Summary

In this deliverable we have demonstrated the prototype of VC. We have provided its overview corresponding to the status at M30 and presented its architecture based on the actor model, explained the dynamic instantiation and execution of PROforma CIGs (introduced earlier this year), and summarized interactions between actors during VC operations. We have also prepared and executed two scenarios that demonstrate a wide range of available coaching interventions -- this is captured in the video associated with this document.

VC has achieved the *release candidate* state -- its two instances have been deployed to dedicated virtual machines hosted by PUT and they continuously operate as part of the development and test platforms. The next steps will be concerned with the following activities:

- Developing additional specialized CIGs capturing new guidelines (e.g., for mucosal injury or cancer-related fatigue) and organizational workflows (e.g., responsible for the cyclic application of questionnaires planned for the CAPABLE clinical study),
- Testing VC in scenarios with multiple patients that will simulate workload comparable to the one expected during the clinical study (some tens of patients),
- Introducing extra measures to further improve the reliability of VC, e.g., a specialized watchdog actor that will constantly monitor the status of other actors in VC and inform the administrator about any encountered problems.

We also continue our research on personalized prediction models for capsules that would choose the appropriate time and motivation message for a capsule given the patient characteristics. The initial results are described in (Lisowska et al., 2021a, 2021b) and we plan to embed these models in VC (through specialized enquiry types), so it can offer even more sophisticated non-pharmacological, personalised wellbeing interventions.

7. Glossary

CIG	Computer-interpretable Guideline
CM	Case Manager
CPG	Clinical Practice Guideline
DE	Deontics Engine
DP	Data Platform
PDSS	Physician Decision Support System
PtApp	Patient App
VC	Virtual Coach

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